

Form and Methods of Formation of Spiritual-Moral Characteristics on the Basis of Labor Education

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Abstract:

In three articles, the forms and methods of developing spiritual and moral abilities of students based on labor education, human moral qualities, behavior, the importance of teaching children to be diligent and spiritual development are covered.

Keywords: hard work, morals, the concept of spirituality, mental balance, spiritual and moral education, well-rounded personality, good qualities.

Humanity and its civilization cannot develop without spirituality, because spirituality is the basis that makes a person human and maintains the spiritual balance between the material world.

The proof of the beginning of life is the fact that all knowledge and experiences, words, concepts, imaginations and lives in the world, directly or indirectly related to human activity, arise, develop, become rich and improve, or become obsolete and become miserable after the end of life. That's why we call it a very unique - phenomenal phenomenon. It is a spiritual phenomenon that has been appreciated in all times, created by a person and society who lives with healthy thoughts and noble dreams. 21st century pedagogy, new discoveries in technology, the process of globalization related to complex processes is changing.

The rapid development of our country in recent years created the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the development of New Uzbekistan. development, unconditional provision of human rights and interests, and active civil society are established. In the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" direction 4 - development of human capital, direction 5 - bringing spiritual development to a new level is

envisaged. . In the development strategy, it depends on the human factor with 100 experiences arranged in 7 directions, that is, on the modern competences of the youth, on the strong spirituality of the youth. Therefore, the new pedagogy of New Uzbekistan is responsible for educating young people who are able to implement these stable directions. accepting it as an order, it is required to add its scientific and practical parts to the development strategy.

Today, we are living in a renewed homeland, which our people and foreigners call New Uzbekistan. Because in the next five years, Uzbekistan has completely changed its face at the national and international professional level. The country's global reputation and status have reached unprecedented levels. was raised.

Another aspect makes people happy. This is New for 2022-2026 In Uzbekistan's development strategy, it is important to achieve spirituality and human capital. Look at the goals 71, 72 and 73 of the strategy: "a healthy worldview and creativity in the society to a national movement", "a book-loving nation", "deep learning of the heritage of great ancestors" Big goals such as "learning and promotion" have been set. Two of the seven directions of the strategy have been devoted to spirituality and human capital. This is very happy. Why?

Because global modernization brings renewal processes and technologies into our lives every day. Machines, equipment, equipment, and technological processes need to be updated and modernized. Outdated knowledge, skills, and qualifications cannot be used. Because these are economic renewal, old goods. What to do? Therefore, every person should always work on himself, gain continuous knowledge and enrich his human capital.

The main goal of Uzbekistan's pedagogy is the necessary production process of the society, the state and the learner, the development of the cultivation of strong moral, highly competent, and entitled personnel who have begun to serve the spiritual, social, and economic development of Uzbekistan. provide they resembled. A teacher-pedagogue who has a broad worldview, thinks independently and freely, can model the educational process in a purposeful way can determine the development of education.

Such a responsibility is assigned to the teacher of New Uzbekistan. How should we pedagogues understand this burden of responsibility? This was explained by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "Another important issue that always worries us is related to the manners, behavior and, in a word, worldview of our youth. Today, times are changing rapidly. "Who will feel the changes the most - young people." Let the young people be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, let them not forget their identity. The call of who we are and the descendants of great people always echoes in their hearts and is true to their identity. Let him encourage you to stay. At what expense will we achieve this? Education, education and only education," he says.

As the great enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat said, the world is a field of struggle, and a healthy body, a sharp mind and good morals are becoming the weapons of this struggle, and it is necessary for us to work on the basis of knowledge and enlightenment. After all, education and spirituality are twin concepts.

The scope of the use of simple labor tools appeared. The increasing complexity created the need to develop effective work skills and competencies in the young generation. Initially, this happened in the process of work and in the heart of the entire social life. Later, education became a separate field of human activity and consciousness. In fact, it has been a constant companion ever since humanity recognized the mind, the difference between the soul and the body, the meaning of life, and the spirituality of goodness. Just as one can foresee the destiny, through spirituality, a person will have the opportunity to imagine history, the present day and the future, and thus produce the necessary lessons and productions.

It is not without reason that spirituality has been further developed as an integral system that opens up a new time with a new look at the precious life of humanity. who strengthened their dignity and identity, centuries

This social phenomenon has deep historical, theoretical and practical foundations, and it is objectively necessary to study it on a holistic and systematic basis in order to understand it in its full content and scope. , is the requirement of today's era.

Spirituality is a mirror that reflects a person's inner world, feelings, personal qualities, and moral qualities. Every nation, every ethnic group, and representative of every religion has its own spiritual world. This is spirituality. . worlds are constantly changing and developing under the influence of time and era. If we are talking about spirituality, first of all it is possible to get acquainted with the meaning and history of the origin of this word. Plab scholars have a past and considerable scientific work that has produced different definitions

Spirituality is a concept that expresses the inner spiritual and conscious way of life of people. It includes intellectual, legal, scientific, behavioral, and religious views of a person. There are two worlds of a person, which are his organization and inner world. . Physical appearance, height, behavior, determine the inner state of a person, it determines his spiritual and moral appearance. In spiritual and moral education, hard work. and interest in the profession is a special profession. Because a person works sincerely for himself, his family, and his country, he should also be able to enjoy it. It is necessary to have time without relying on teachers.

Morality - (Arabic plural of behavior, Latin *moralis* - behavior) - a phenomenon of spiritual life, one of the forms of social consciousness, a concept related to the field of spirituality. Historically formed behavior, behavior, social and personal behavior of people. a set of stable, specific norms and rules that regulate interactions in life, as well as relationships with society.

Moral education is an important social phenomenon in the life of the society, a form of inculcating the moral system and moral qualities into the consciousness of each generation based on modern requirements. Moral education is a scientific category studied by the sciences of literature, psychology, ethics and aesthetics. Moral education is understood as a system of scientific and practical actions aimed at forming human qualities in the growing generation that correspond to the norms of behavior and meet the requirements of the time. understands moral values through education, develops moral experiences, skills and qualities, learns to live on the basis of moral standards and principles.

Industriousness is a spiritual virtue that expresses personal diligence, appreciation of work, work, and a person's attitude to work in general. His help is measured by the amount and quality of the yield or product. The opposite of hard work is laziness, laziness, laziness. In any society, efforts are made to educate young people in the spirit of hard work. destroys the development of family, community and society. Hardworking individual and society is one of the important qualities of spirituality. Without hard work, there would be no spirituality

Morality means, first of all, a sense of fairness and justice, faith, honesty. Our ancient ancestors developed a whole set of moral requirements for a perfect person, in modern terms, they developed an oriental code of ethics. A lot of work is being done in this regard in the family, at school and in the wider neighborhood.

In the new era, a new worldview and new thinking are required. Therefore, today, education has begun to respond to the quality of the day, the production of new methods that can serve the interests of the whole society and people, and new benefits during this period, especially in the next five years, some serious work is being done. From the day a child is born, his parents, but also the whole society, are financially responsible for him.

An education system organized in accordance with world standards for individual children will play an important role in maintaining the quality of future education. programs have been drawn up and are being implemented year-round and continuously.

Preschoolers are known to be very inquisitive and their memory needs to receive information according to their age. As children are inculcated with humane and noble abilities, they will grow up to be strong individuals with a strong will to stand up for themselves in any problematic product and work.

There are different types of students' labor activities, they are planting:

1. Domestic work;
2. Educational work;
3. Power production work;
4. Technical work;
5. Socially productive work;
6. Social - useful work and others.

The main idea of labor education is to create a person to work, to develop skills and abilities, to value social work, and to educate the character of hard work.

In conclusion, it can be said that the importance of work and work education is incomparable in his life, in his physical and spiritual education and in reaching high maturity. Work develops after helping family members. Through this, the child develops love for work, and skills and productivity for the future. Child education is gradually being carried out in kindergartens, schools, colleges and higher education institutions will help.

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